

Getting Rid of ‘Either Or’ in Processes of Digitalization and De-Digitalization of Schools? The Digital Pencil as Boundary Object

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Introduction

All over the world, the pencil is one of the most prominent and well known symbols of education and schooling. It is one of the first objects that children encounter when they start school, if not before that – in their private homes, when drawing and practicing their first literacy skills, and in preschool and kindergarten. It is a reasonably cheap object, easy to maintain; it only needs a sharpening every now and then. Its uses are also highly diverse. A pencil can be used to do calculations, to create handwritten texts, to draw, and to combine writing and illustrations into *multimodal* texts. It can also be used for inscriptions on the walls and doors of school toilets, or on the desks in the classroom. And all the aforementioned types of inscription can quite easily be removed with the simple use of an eraser – another reasonably cheap and globally available object.

The pencil, along with notebooks and other types of school-related stationery, is also a symbol of *analogue* school practices. In many parts of the world, such analogue practices, involving blackboards, pencils and paper, still dominate the educational systems. However, in some parts of the world – mostly, but not exclusively, in the Global North – the last 25 years or so have been influenced by both practices and discourses of digitalization. The Scandinavian countries stand out here, but so do other countries in Northern Europe, North America and, for instance, in South Korea (Ayhan, 2024). It is fair to say that on a global scale, access to digital tools in education is unevenly distributed. As we will show below, Tilya (2018) and others have pointed to how most of the countries in sub-Saharan Africa have yet not been affected by these practices and discourses of digitalization.

In a country like Sweden, where we are active as researchers in the broader fields of *technology in education*, *new literacy studies*, and *multimodality*, the Digitalisation Commission was created in 2012 with the goal ‘that Sweden should become the best in the world at exploiting the opportunities of digitalization’ (SOU 2015, p.28). Obviously, the ambitions were high, and even before the establishment of the Digitalisation Commission the endeavour of digitalizing schools had materialized into so-called ‘one-to-one’ computing projects (cf. Björkvall, 2015; Björkvall and Engblom, 2010; Jacquet, 2016). This development gained momentum in the early 2000s, and the idea behind such projects is simple: every learner is provided with their own laptop or tablet with which they perform most of their school work. Such projects are quite well researched in Sweden, and there

are obvious advantages with working with digital tools in the classroom. For instance, all the texts and all information available on the internet can be accessed by the learners; many textbooks and other learning resources are directly available through the device – including those of generative AI; dialogues between teachers and learners can take place also outside of the physical classroom; and a wide array of resources for multimodal meaning-making through writing, image, typography, film etc. are made available. As a result, texts were created through the use of keyboards on laptops or tablets and text layout programmes that invited the use of sound, image and music in the creation of *multimodal ensembles* (Bezemer and Kress, 2016; Kress, 2010).

A problem, in hindsight, may have been that in many cases, pens, paper and traditional textbooks were not used at all, or very sparsely, in classrooms. Some Swedish learners did not learn how to write by hand, for instance, and critical voices were raised regarding the benefits of using analogue resources when doing mathematics or taking notes (cf. Siegel, 2021). The advantages of reading longer, linear texts in the shape and form of printed (text) books were also discussed. This critique has become more prominent over the years, and now Sweden is in what can be called a state of ‘de-digitalization’ of its educational system, at least in compulsory school (Grades 1-9), which has also been observed in the international press (The Guardian, 2023). This agenda is pushed by researchers in, for instance, cognitive science – pointing to cognitive advantages of analogue tools, especially for younger learners – but also through political initiatives (cf. Utbildningsdepartementet, 2022).

In Sweden, the contours of an ‘either or’ approach to digital and analogue tools in education are visible – a type of dichotomization where schools are either totally committed to using digital tools or totally removing them from their literacy practices. As researchers in the field of literacy and education, we reject such dichotomies. Instead, in this article we point to key concepts in the field of multimodality: *aptness* and *interest* of sign-makers (Kress, 2010; Bezemer and Kress, 2016). These concepts point to how the tools and resources that are most apt for performing a certain task should always be given priority: in some cases this is an advanced digital tool for text creation, in other cases perhaps an analogue pencil and an eraser. The issue is not digital or analogue – the goals and interests of learners and educators are.

With the development in Sweden as a backdrop – and with a specific focus on uses of *digital* pencils (see below) in education – we will argue that there are conclusions to be drawn that may be relevant for shaping educational policies for digitalization in education in contexts and places where the digitalization – for various reasons – has not yet gained momentum and where educational policies can still be adjusted so that dichotomies between digital and analogue tools are avoided. For us, these contexts very broadly include sub-Saharan Africa, including Seychelles and South Africa – two countries that together with Mauritius are usually viewed as more digitalized than other countries in sub-Saharan Africa (Tilya, 2018; International Telecommunication Union, 2024).

Based on an analysis of data collected in a grade four and a grade eight class in Sweden, this article focuses on an object whose uses are located at the intersection of digital and analogue practices: the digital pencil. With the shape of an analogue pencil, it can be used as a provider of ‘digital ink’ on the screen of a tablet or specific types of laptops, but it also has other functions for marking objects, moving them and designing different layers in drawings and images.

The aim of the article is to explore how the introduction and use of digital pencils in schools can obstruct or at least soften the type of digital-analogue dichotomy described above.¹ Two research questions are addressed.

- ◆ How can digital pencils – as a type of *boundary object* – connect literacy practices, in fully digitalized classrooms, to their analogue counterparts? Boundary objects are artefacts that through their functionality and design can connect practices across domains (cf. Star and Griesemer, 1989 and Wenger, 1998 and our more extensive definition in the section ‘Analytical framework’, below)?
- ◆ And more speculatively, what is the potential of digital pencils to function as boundary objects for introducing digital literacies in fully analogue classrooms, in this case in sub-Saharan Africa?²

The second research question forms the foundation for a concluding discussion of how to prevent emerging processes of digitalization in sub-Saharan Africa to construe an ‘either or’ relation between digital and analogue tools for learning and meaning-making.

In the following, we present short overviews of research on digitalization of education in sub-Saharan Africa and Sweden, respectively. By no means do we suggest that sub-Saharan Africa and Sweden are comparable entities, but the aim is to give an overview of the status of digitalization in some African countries in order to be able to relate this to the digitalization of compulsory schools in Sweden – the context from which our analysis departs. After this research overview, we present the data and analytical framework in more detail, before we move on to present the results. The article concludes with a

¹ The two studies presented here were both part of the project *Connecting digital and analog literacy: The potential of the digital pencil for text creation in schools (DigiPen)*. The research was financed by Örebro University and the University of Arts, Crafts and Design (‘Konstfack’) in Sweden, and the hardware company Logitech. Logitech provided the learners and teachers that participated in the study with digital pencils. They also co-financed the salary of one of the researchers, so that the study in grade eight could be performed. However, Logitech had no influence over aims or research questions and has not in any way influenced how the results have been interpreted. All this was agreed upon at the outset of the project.

² Anders Björkqvall would like to thank the Stellenbosch Institute for Advanced Study (STIAS), South Africa, for offering such a creative environment for finalizing this article.

discussion of the potential of digital pencils in relation to digital-analogue dichotomies, and we answer the research questions more extensively.

Research on digitalization of education in sub-Saharan Africa and Sweden

To start with, it seems that the digitalization of education in sub-Saharan Africa is generally under researched, also in, for instance, the South African context. UNESCO reports on pilot projects on ICT (Information and Communication Technology) use in Rwanda, Mozambique and Zimbabwe. These projects have been carried out in order to train teachers in ICT skills, develop and make accessible digital materials and resources, and to establish policies on ICT in education (UNESCO, 2020). As an example, the projects in Mozambique and Zimbabwe focused on enhancing teachers' ICT skills and their ability to integrate ICT tools in education, for instance by creating so-called e-school models and equipping teachers and learners with laptops, projectors and routers, to be used in the classroom. A more recent example of ICT initiatives is the Africa Digital Schools Initiative, with the aim of increasing ICT competencies in teachers in Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, Ghana, and Nigeria. An evaluation of the experiences of teachers who participated in the programme highlighted an increased ICT proficiency for the participating teachers, although the transfer of these skills into actual classroom practice appears to have been less explored (Agyei, 2021).

In his overview of ICT in primary and secondary education in sub-Saharan Africa, Tilya (2018) highlights several barriers for implementing ICT in the region, such as a lack of sufficient funding, a lack of infrastructure (access to electricity, internet and computers, etc.), and a need for teacher training and coordination of ICT initiatives. In schools where digital devices are made available, the devices are not always used effectively due to a lack of teachers trained in ICT pedagogy, and often strategies for incorporating ICT into education are lacking (Tilya, 2018, p.1304).

Countries in the region are currently at different stages of their implementation of ICT in education. In terms of ICT policies, some countries have implemented ICT in both primary and secondary school, sometimes across grades and subjects, or as a specific subject; whereas in other countries ICT is only present in upper secondary school. In a few cases, there are no formal ICT recommendations or policies (Tilya, 2018, p.1309). Looking at different stages of adopting and using ICT in education, most countries are in what can be termed 'emerging' or 'applying' stage, which consists of learning how to use ICT and adapting the curriculum to increase the use of ICT. Only Seychelles, Mauritius and South Africa can be said to be at an 'infusing' stage, which entails understanding how to use ICT, which tools are apt for what tasks, and integrating ICT across the curriculum (Tilya, 2018, p.1308, p.1311). Tilya concludes: 'Despite the development of ICT in education policies, use of ICT in education is still at an embryonic stage in most [sub-

Saharan African – SSA] countries; the integration of technology in classrooms across SSA remains insufficient to meet the needs of the twenty-first-century labor market.’ (2018, p.1306). However, he adds that in South Africa, for instance, we should not forget that there are substantial differences between the cities and rural areas when it comes to access to ICT (p.1312).

Importantly, it should be noted – which Tilya also does – that the use of mobile phones has increased enormously in sub-Saharan Africa. There is even talk of a ‘mobile revolution’ sweeping the region, with mobile phone use spreading quickly, geographically, and socially, accompanied by novel applications’ (Tilya, 2018, p.1303). This also has educational implications. Mobile devices may be cheaper, easier to use and more easily accessible and can be used to access text, and to write with. ICT integration in education can be achieved without traditional laptops and computers.

Turning specifically to the Seychelles, reports on the development of ICT in education highlight that the country has a rather developed infrastructure compared to other countries in sub-Saharan Africa (Isaacs, 2007, p.3). The country has also been ranked as one of the countries with the highest levels of ICT development (International Telecommunication Union, 2024). Nonetheless, Medor’s (2022) study on novice teachers’ perceptions of their profession shows that access to computers and internet is one of the main challenges teachers face, whereas applying ICT skills was deemed less of a challenge (pp.82-83). It is also worth noting that as of 2025, the school curriculum includes a number of digital skills (Capmad, 2024).

With respect to Sweden, the digitalization of Swedish schools can be said to be extensive. Statistics of the number of digital devices in Swedish schools show that almost all learners in compulsory school and upper secondary school have access to their own digital device through their school (Skolverket, 2022, pp.42-43). As a result, laptops and tablets are nowadays considered as standard tools for teaching and learning in Sweden (Hall et al., 2021). In terms of education and designs for learning, the technology available in Swedish schools implies that a fully digitalized environment is (or could be) the starting point for any activity involving writing, text creation and drawing in the vast majority of Swedish classrooms.

From an historical perspective, ideas of the digitalization of schools in Sweden have been present since around the 1970s, although the scale and type of initiatives has varied (Jedekog, 2007; Fransson et al., 2018). From the 1970s onwards, a number of campaigns to introduce ICT and digital tools have been carried out (Jedekog, 2007, p.6), for instance, by providing schools with computers and introducing computer knowledge in the national curriculum (Söderlund, 2000, p.67). Initiatives and campaigns during the early 2000s have continued to advocate for digital tools and ICT in schools, with initiatives aimed at, for instance, teachers in the form of courses (Gustafsson, 2024, p.16). During this period, the number of students per computer or digital device decreased (Skolverket, 2013, p.6).

Recurrent follow-ups conducted by the National Agency for Education on the implementation of digital tools have shown that while access to these tools is generally good in all levels of education in Sweden (Skolverket, 2016, p.4), there is still a need for teachers to develop their competences, for instance, when it comes to selecting apt digital resources for their teaching (Skolverket, 2022, p.5).

The actual implementation of the digitalization strategies outlined in government policy documents has varied depending on the municipality and organization, as shown by Gustafsson (2024). In some cases, schools are provided with ample resources, but actual policy and implementation are left to individual schools, whereas some municipalities also developed more specific approaches and detailed local policies describing how the national digitalization strategy should be enacted (Gustafsson, 2024, pp.70-71). Similarly, the policy can be difficult to interpret and, thus, implement in teaching. In their analysis of the national strategy of digitalization proposed by the Swedish National Agency for Education, Fransson et al. (2018) show that the notion of 'adequate digital competence' that is brought forward in the strategy is vague and elusive: what counts as adequate digital competence is context dependent, changes over time, and can be interpreted differently by different actors involved – teachers, students and school leaders (p.224).

As a result of these processes of digitalization, 'one-to-one' computing can be viewed as a completed reform in the Swedish educational system. Reviews of this reform, both in a Swedish context and in an international one, point to both positive and negative outcomes. The international review presented by Islam and Grönlund (2016) points to both positive effects of introducing ICT, such as increased student motivation and computing skills, and negative ones, such as logistic and technical challenges, as well as resistance from teachers (p.213). In terms of the effects on student performance, there are contrasting results, and overall a lack of robust studies investigating the results of such 'one-to-one' interventions (Sirajul Islam and Grönlund, 2016, p.194). From a Swedish perspective, a study by Hall et al. (2021) does not show any significant effects on students' performance on standardized tests in mathematics or languages after implementing 'one-to-one' computing. Neither is there any indication that this intervention has decreased the digital divide and inequality in schools (Hall et al., 2021, p.32), which has often been one of the arguments in favour of digitalization.

ICT and the introduction of digital resources have also been evaluated from a teacher perspective. Here, studies show that the use of ICT and digital devices in Sweden presents teachers with a number of challenges when it comes to teaching preparations. Teachers report that it is time consuming to find digital resources and learn how to use different applications, and that there is a need for up-to-date technical knowledge about apps and software (Ekberg and Gao, 2018; Lindberg et al., 2017; Tallvid, 2015).

The digitalization of Swedish schools has led to research that specifically zooms in on the differences between digital and analogue practices, comparing digital literacy and writing

on a computer with the analogue practices of writing and shaping by hand. For example, previous studies have compared digital and analogue writing in terms of writing strategies, formal correctness, and quality (e.g. Åkerfeldt, 2014; Dahlström and Boström, 2017; Erixon, 2018; Hultin and Westman, 2013). In other words, research has often had a contrastive perspective on the use of digital and analogue tools in classrooms, and discourses around teaching and learning still tend to construe a dichotomy between ‘digital’ and ‘traditional’/‘analogue’ practices. This division is perhaps relevant in relation to issues of a technological nature, but inconsistent with how people use resources for various purposes in everyday meaning-making practices.

As touched upon in the introduction, this divide between the digital and the analogue can also be seen in the changed political messages regarding digitalization in schools. Today, ideas of de-digitalization prevail in the public debate about digitalization in Swedish schools. Teachers and students should now discard the digital tools in favour of analogue practices in the form of printed textbooks etc., and use analogue pencils as opposed to a keyboard or the finger on the tablet. From viewing digital devices as a means for economic, political, intellectual and educational progress, the debate about digitalization has taken a more sceptical turn, and points to risks with spending too much time in front of screens.

This research review highlights the fact that there are obvious differences in the degree of digitalization of education in a country like Sweden and almost all of the sub-Saharan African countries. Sweden is highly digitalized; sub-Saharan Africa much less so, and this also goes for Seychelles, Mauritius and South Africa, even if they are at what Tilya (2018) calls an ‘infusing stage’. Thus, there are still significant strategic choices to be made and strategies to be fulfilled regarding digitalization of education in sub-Saharan Africa. We want to raise a few points related to analogue and digital literacies that can be relevant before such choices are made – and we draw our examples from our studies of uses of digital pencils in Sweden.

Previous research on digital pencils

Although there are ample studies on the uses of digital tools in education, fewer studies have focused on the digital pencil as a specific tool. Instead, there has been a tendency to use the digital pencil as a metaphor to refer to a broad range of digital devices – keyboards, laptops, tablets, etc. – which has left the specific uses and potentials of digital pencils less explored in research (cf. Farinosi et al., 2016; Lei et al., 2008; Wollscheid et al., 2016).

In the context of education, previous research on digital pencils has mainly focused on their uses in higher education (e.g., Huang et al., 2017; Siddiqui and Muntjir, 2017), but there are a few examples of studies on younger children’s use of digital pencils in schools, such as the study by Lubke and Dabney (2017) on children’s annotations with digital pencils, and Simonnet et al. (2019), who focused on children’s shaping of letters. As shown

by Lubke and Dabney (2017, p.51), the children made use of and experienced the potentials of the digital pencil in ways that were not predicted by their teachers. For example, the children commented on the ‘mess-free’ erasing of texts when using the digital pencil (as opposed to an analogue one and an eraser, which can leave marks).

Another strand of research has focused more on the physical properties of the digital pencil. For instance, Riche et al. (2017) makes a distinction between the digital pencil as a provider of ‘digital ink’, and the digital pencil as a multifunctional tool for various tasks, such as moving items on the screen, clicking on apps or using the ‘lasso’ function to capture and transform content. In our own previous studies (Björkvall et al., 2025a, 2025b), we saw a dominance of this ‘digital ink’ function in how the learners made use of the pencils, but also some examples of how the digital pencil was used as a more multifunctional tool with specific functions that go beyond the ones we recognise from analogue pencils.

Similarly focusing on the physical properties, studies have investigated the potentials of using the digital pencil as a tool for helping older users to handle technology (Hourcade and Berkel, 2008; Valentine et al., 2017), and have analysed differences in the texture of the screen surface in relation to writing practices (Alamargot and Morin, 2015; Guilbert et al., 2019; Hochhauser et al., 2021; Park et al., 2012). In relation to the latter, it appears as though the lack of friction on the screen of a tablet affects young learners who are starting to write. In the aforementioned study by Björkvall et al. (2025b) the learners’ way of holding the pencil, and the positioning of the pencil in relation to the screen, also stood out as factors to consider when introducing digital pencils to young learners.

Data

A broad set of data form the foundation for our analysis of how digital pencils – as boundary objects, see below – can potentially soften digital-analogue dichotomies in schools and connect digital literacy practices to analogue practices of inscription by hand. We have collected the data in two classes in Swedish compulsory school: one fourth-grade class and one eighth-grade class.

The data were collected in two iPad schools in Sweden, where learners work with iPads across subjects. All in all, four teachers – two from grade four and two from grade eight – participated and 76 learners (53 from grade four and 23 from grade eight). It is important to point out that most of the learners had no previous experience of working with digital pencils. In that sense, the pencils were just ‘thrown into’ the literacy practices of the classrooms and neither teachers nor learners were provided with any training, neither from us nor from Logitech, the hardware company that provided the project with digital pencils (see footnote 1). However, they were all given time to explore the digital pencil in relation to their iPads, and we asked the teachers to stick to their original lesson plans, but try to think of exercises where digital pencils could potentially be useful.

The data are presented in Table 1. Every data type is commented upon in the rightmost column.

Table 1: Data types and quantity of collected data (cf. Björkqvall et al., 2025a, p.15)

Data type	Quantity grade 4/8	Comments
Video recordings	76/75 recordings (9 hours, 42 minutes, 55 seconds/5 hours, 47 minutes, 14 seconds)	The recordings were mostly produced through handheld cameras, sometimes complemented by the use of a fixed camera (documenting work in groups).
Photos	91/43 photos	The photos are mostly of texts and drawings, and the pencil as part of the production process.
Field notes	11/11 field notes (11.5 pages, 4856 words/12 pages, 4963 words)	The field notes were produced by the three researchers/authors of this report individually.
Group interviews	1 teacher interview (22 minutes, 16 seconds), 2 student focus group interviews (46 minutes, 29 seconds in total)/1 teacher interview (19 minutes, 21 seconds), 1 student focus group interview (33 minutes, 49 seconds)	The group interviews were video recorded.
Learners' texts	Approximately 25/50 texts	Sometimes these texts were captured by our photos and video recordings, so it is difficult to give an exact number of texts collected.

The video recordings and the photos helped us capture the literacy practices in which digital pencils were actually used and the texts or drawings that were created or worked upon. However, these data types also include practices where, most commonly, the index finger or keyboard were used instead of the digital pencil. The field notes include reflections upon the practices and uses identified, but also ideas that came up during the

fieldwork and notes on what was important for us to remember in order to interpret what is going on in the video and photo data.

The interviews with the teachers helped us to identify the teachers' opinions on the usability, problems and potentials of the digital pencil. The focus group interviews were performed in order to capture similar issues from the learners' perspectives, but also to get a sense of their attitudes to, for instance, hand writing and digital as well as analogue pencils. Finally, the texts collected gave us information of what textual products can actually be created with digital pencils, under the conditions that were described above.

An application of ethical review was sent to the Swedish Ethical Review Authority. The project was assessed as not falling under the provisions of the Ethical Review Act. Instead, an advisory opinion was issued in which it was stated that the authority did not have any ethical objections to the research project. Before any data was collected, learners, teachers and caretakers gave their consent to participating in the studies. A very restricted number of learners did not want to participate, and they were simply not documented.

Analytical framework

Two main analytical frameworks in combination form the foundation for the analysis. *Multimodal ethnography* (Björkvall, 2012; Flewitt, 2011) combines ethnographic perspectives on – most commonly – various types of literacy practices with *social semiotic* perspectives on meaning-making (Kress, 2010; 2011). This is reflected in our data (Table 1). We analysed both the practices in which digital pencils are used and the artefact – the pencil – and the text or drawings it was used to create. Inspired by ethnography, we returned several times to the respective classrooms in order to follow the projects in which the pencils were used over time. Social semiotics helped us to think about the potentials of digital pencils as tools for meaning-making: what can be done with them, and what is better done with other tools for inscription? Here, *affordance*, is a key concept, which we return to below.

In addition, the *designs for learning* approach (Björklund Boistrup and Selander, 2022; Selander and Kress, 2021) highlights *design* and *agency* in relation to digital pencils. Teachers design *for* learning through, for instance, preparing literacy tasks in which the pencils can be put to use. Learners design *in* learning when creating texts, drawings and perhaps other artefacts with (or without) digital pencils on their iPads.

Even though our analytical framework draws on insights from both these theories, two concepts play key roles in the analysis. The first is that of *affordance*. Originally introduced by the ecological psychologist Gibson (1979) as the potentials and constraints that human (and animals) perceive in their environment, it has been used in a more specific way in social semiotic and multimodal research: 'The history of semiotic use of a specific

materiality produces *semiotic affordances*: what a sign-maker does is shaped by what other sign-makers have done before her or him, in response to similar social and semiotic needs.’ (Bezemer and Kress, 2016, p.31, italics in original.) The ‘materiality’ in our case is the pencils along with screens, perhaps school desks, etc. More precisely, digital pencils invite – or afford – certain uses more than other ones through their design. For instance, digital pencils afford being used for more detailed inscription on a glossy surface than for inscription on rougher surfaces (whereas some analogue pens and pencils require some friction in order to function correctly). The uses of digital pencils are both enabled and restricted by the design, but also by the users’ knowledge of previous uses of analogue as well as digital pencils. Thus, the concept of affordance ties together literacy practices, (social) semiotic perspectives on artefacts and meaning-making, and design theoretical views of learning: we study the affordances of digital pencils when they are put to use in literacy practices in classrooms.

But that is not enough. We also use the concept of *boundary object* (Star and Griesemer, 1989; cf. Wenger, 1998) in order to think about how digital pencils can function as artefacts that connect analogue practices from school contexts that basically do not use any digital tools to practices in more digitalized classrooms – and vice versa. Star and Griesemer explain how boundary objects can work among museum workers.

This [boundary object] is an analytic concept of those scientific objects which both inhabit several intersecting social worlds (...) and satisfy the informational requirements of each of them. Boundary objects are objects which are both plastic enough to adapt to local needs and the constraints of the several parties employing them, yet robust enough to maintain a common identity across sites. They are weakly structured in common use, and become strongly structured in individual site use. These objects may be abstract or concrete. They have different meanings in different social worlds but their structure is common enough to more than one world to make them recognizable, a means of translation. The creation and management of boundary objects is a key process in developing and maintaining coherence across intersecting social worlds.

(Star and Griesemer, 1989, p.393.)

Digital pencils share some properties of the boundary objects identified by Star and Griesemer. They are primarily put to work in the digital world, but connect through their design to the analogue world. They are weakly structured in the sense that they can be used for an array of semiotic and literacy tasks, but become very structured when put to semiotic use in writing, drawing, calculating etc. Above all, digital pencils are so similar to analogue pencils in their design, that they will be recognized as pencils in both the digital and analogue world. Finally, but most importantly, we are interested in knowing if digital pencils can be used for ‘developing and maintaining coherence across intersecting social worlds’ (Star and Griesemer, 1989, p.393), that is, across classrooms at various stages of a digitalization – or de-digitalization – process.

The digital pencil as a boundary object between analogue and digital literacy practices

Our analysis points to various degrees to which digital pencils either recontextualize analogue literacy practices, or are used in more distinct and unique ways. This can be illustrated as a continuum of literacy practices which involves the digital pencil as a boundary object (Figure 1).

Figure 1: A continuum of literacy practices involving the digital pencil

The two arrowheads on the line in Figure 1 indicate a continuum on which literacy practices involving digital pencils can be placed, and do not point to anything outside of the figure (such as a time period before analogue literacy practices, for instance). In literacy practices placed all the way to the right on the line in Figure 1, we find uses of the digital pencil which closely relate to how analogue pens and pencils have been used in analogue literacy practices which we recognize from non-digitalized classrooms and traditional schooling. On the opposite end of the continuum we find literacy practices which make use of the multifunctionality of the digital pencil as a tool for various types of tasks, such as moving items, clicking and designing a text in layers (cf. Riche et al., 2017). In between these outer poles, we find practices that fall somewhere in-between, connecting both analogue and digital aspects of using pencils. For instance, the digital pencil can be used together with a paper sheet with analogue notes in the same workflow. The idea of viewing literacy practices as placed on an analogue-digital continuous line (Figure 1) will structure how we present our main results below. It also provides us with a way of discussing potential uses of digital pencils as boundary objects between primarily digital and primarily analogue classrooms.

To the right in Figure 1, we place uses of the digital pencil that pick up and obviously recontextualize analogue literacy practices, such as writing with a pen on a piece of paper or in a notebook. An example of this use is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Writing with the digital pencil, similar to analogue literacy practices

Figure 2 shows two eighth-grade learners working on an assignment in art class, which consists of completing an image analysis and answering questions by means of a textbook. The analysis and the answers to the questions are written down and documented on the iPad. As is visible in Figure 2, the iPad is placed flat on the desk, similar to how the textbook in the right hand side of the image is placed. This horizontal, on-desk, positioning of the screen, along with how the learners are holding their digital pencils and resting their hands on the screens of the iPads suggests a close relation to the practice of using pen and paper. The ‘digital ink’ provided by the digital pencil is used on a material surface for inscription, in this case a screen, something we recognize from the practice of writing down answers in a notebook.

Figure 3 shows two more examples of how affordances of analogue artefacts and materials are recontextualized into a digitalized classroom.

Figure 3: Two examples of manual inscription with the digital pencil

In the image to the left, a fourth-grade learner is using the digital pencil to complete a word search task. In this case, the printed stencil format is recontextualized into a digitalized classroom in the form of a pdf file. Unlike in Figure 2, the spatial orientation of the screen is here slightly tilted and more vertical. The learner’s grip of the pencil is also higher, more

indicative of a finger or a stylus pen used for pressing or clicking than many analogue pencils used for manual inscription. The positioning of the screen and this way of holding the pencil is, however, not completely separate from the use of print books or highlighter pens, but it is less associated with traditional school writing.

In the image to the right in Figure 3, another fourth-grade learner is working on a task that consists of writing in runic letters and filling out a timeline of the Viking Age. Again, we see the printed stencil – a type of worksheet – turned digital, and the screen is similarly more vertically placed, this time using the screen cover. The learner can be seen holding the digital pencil in their hand as they zoom in and out on the timeline, which differs from analogue inscription that does not allow for this type of hand movement. However, the task of writing in runic letters with a tool for inscription – in this case a digital pencil – very much points to analogue literacies and previous cultures of inscription.

In fully digitalized classrooms, this shows that the digital pencil can function as a boundary object to enable the recognition of the *provenance* (semiotic origin of the practice, cf. Kress and van Leeuwen, 2001, p.73) of these literacy practices. Compared to the manual inscription shown in Figure 2, we would, however, place the uses in Figure 3 slightly further to the left on the continuum in Figure 1, as the affordances picked up by the learners are not solely analogue ones, but rather affordances of digital literacies, in the form of a more tilted iPad angle which affords a different relation between the learner's body and screen (people also tilt analogue books and writing surfaces, but judging from our field study this is quite systematically done with the iPad), and the interplay between pencil and hand as the learner zooms in and out on the screen.

Our fieldwork also documented other uses of the digital pencil which similarly can be placed to the right on the continuum represented in Figure 1. One example is the use of the digital pencil as a cognitive tool for thinking, unloading or relaxing, for instance, when learners made use of the digital pencil to follow along in a text when reading, or used it to tap their leg, scratch their heads, or twirl their hair. These uses were frequent in both studies, and clearly connect to how analogue pencils have been used many years before digital pencils existed.

The digital pencil was also frequently put to use in creative practices, what we call practices of 'playing with shapes'. The potential to use the digital pencil to draw, doodle and test out shapes and letters – and then erase them without a trace – appeared to present the learners with a joyful opportunity for creative play that is otherwise not present – or not as easily accessible – in fully digitalized classrooms. Again, this points to the potential of the digital pencil to function as a boundary object that connects digital classrooms to analogue literacy practices.

Looking more to the middle of the continuum represented in Figure 1, we find examples of literacy practices where analogue and digital literacies were enacted together, at

different stages of an assignment or in a workflow. An example of this is the blackout poetry assignment carried out by the eighth-graders we studied. Figure 4 captures a moment in the process of creating these poems, along with an example of the finished product.

Figure 4: Analogue and digital as different steps of the process

In this assignment, learners were tasked with creating a poem by manipulating a page of a novel that they had been reading in class. By blacking out words on the page, the words left untouched form a poem. As is evident in Figure 4, the learners moved between analogue and digital practices in their work on this assignment. The analogue book page was the starting point, visible as the sheets of paper in the image to the left. To manipulate the text and create a poem, the learners then photographed the book page they selected with the iPad camera, and edited the photo in an illustration software available to them through their school. Here, learners employed various techniques, such as using the digital pencil to circle the words that were to be included in the poem and blackening everything else, or by inserting black text boxes, and using the pencil to move these text boxes around, which resulted in texts as the one to the right in Figure 4. Some learners also did the opposite, that is, highlighting the words in the poem and leaving the rest be. The affordances of the digital pencil offered the learners multiple ways of interacting with an existing text, and, importantly, the option to start over without leaving a trace. At the same time, this literacy practice remains connected to analogue literacy practices, with the written book at the core of the task.

To the left on the continuum in Figure 1, near the extended use of digital potentials, we place uses of the digital pencil which do not have an obvious equivalent in either analogue use of pencils or in analogue literacy practices more broadly speaking. Our analysis shows that learners made use of the digital pencils in a variety of ways to interact with the iPad screen. For instance, learners used the pencil to press on apps, to click on specific functions within apps, to scroll with the pencil, or to browse web pages or the content of apps. These uses are exemplified in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Clicking and scrolling with the digital pencil

In the image to the left in Figure 5, the learner is using the pencil to press the eraser button in the upper right corner to delete the previous edits. In the image to the right in Figure 5, the learner can be seen using the pencil to scroll on the iPad, switching between the display of apps on the home screen to find the app they need to complete their schoolwork. In both cases, the iPad screens are more vertical in their position and placed tilted in the iPad case, and the grip of the pencil is slightly higher than what we saw for the handwriting in Figure 2. This suggests that the digital pencil is used more as a pointer than as a tool for inscription.

Another way of making use of the functions specific to the digital pencil is to use it to design texts in layers, or to create presentations. The latter is exemplified in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Creating and animating a presentation

In the four image compilation in Figure 6, an eighth-grade learner makes use of the digital pencil to create and animate a presentation, dragging and moving the text boxes around to suit their needs. This specific way of using the digital pencil was also commented on by

the eighth-grade learners in the focus group as particularly useful, as it enables more attention to detail.

When making use of the extended functions of the digital pencils, we noted a difference between the two grades. Besides making use of the digital pencil as a provider of ‘digital ink’ in practices of inscription, the fourth-graders mainly used the pencil to click on apps or scroll, as exemplified in Figure 5. The eighth-graders on the other hand also recognized extended functions of the digital pencil, and used it to design and edit texts and drawings in different layers, as well as to create presentations and move text boxes around (as exemplified in Figure 6). This difference between the two grades can be traced back to both the design of the tasks which the learners were asked to complete, and to compatibility issues between the pencil and some of the software used in grade four. This might have restricted the fourth-graders’ ability to recognize some of the affordances of the digital pencil as a tool for text creation and design.

Discussion

The focus of this article has been on how digital pencils in schools potentially mitigate between analogue and digital literacy practices and help to avoid unnecessary digital-analogue dichotomies in processes of digitalization (and in some cases, de-digitalization). Figure 7 shows a way of thinking about how digital pencils can function as boundary objects in contexts of more or less digitalized classrooms. We use Figure 7 as a point of departure for our concluding discussion.

Figure 7: Digital pencils as boundary objects in processes of digitalization

The left box of Figure 7 can roughly be interpreted as representing a classroom in which digitalization has come quite far. That is, typically a classroom found in Sweden rather than in sub-Saharan Africa (Tilya, 2018). Looking at the top of the box, there will be screens in this classroom, typically touch screens. In the lower right we find digital formats such as apps or pdf files together with which a digital pencil can be used. Bottom left includes the learner's body in relation to the screen. In combination with the digital pencil, all these offer a number of affordances of digital literacies. Learners pick up and recognize some of these, and leave some of them untapped. The main point here is that they are affordances of *digital* literacies.

The right box in Figure 7 represents a classroom in which analogue tools dominate, that is, a typical sub-Saharan African classroom (Tilya, 2018) rather than a Swedish one. Here, paper is found at the top and analogue formats such as stencils or notebooks dominate. The relevant embodied literacy relation is that between learners' bodies and paper; pens or probably pencils dominate as the preferred tool for inscription. The affordances in the classroom are those of analogue literacy practices: pencil inscriptions afford erasing (or leaving be); pen inscriptions on paper are more or less permanent; handwriting dominates over typing, etc.

Our analysis has showed that the uses of the digital pencils can roughly be described as being either closely related to those of analogue pencils in analogue literacy practices; or more exclusively involve functions unique to digital pencils; or, finally, combine digital functions of digital pencils with typically analogue literacy practices, as when working with blackout poetry. If we start to look at the typical digital classroom represented to the left in Figure 7, we argue that the digital pencil can function as a boundary object connecting to (often, more historically grounded) analogue literacies. More precisely, in their design *for* learning, teachers can design tasks that will help the learners relate to how other analogue tools for inscription work. For instance, such tasks can include highlighting and commenting on certain parts of a text or to take handwritten notes from a classmate's presentation.

To take a very concrete and relevant example, if a learner is allowed to practice handwriting with a digital pencil they will not only practice how to use digital pencils for this purpose, they will also practice handwriting as a skill to be used in analogue environments, when writing a shopping list or a short instruction, for instance. So, creating learning activities with digital pencils that make relevant practices to the right in Figure 1 will actualize the boundary object potential of the digital pencil for connecting to the world of analogue literacies. Similarly, designing literacy activities in which the digital pencil is preferably used together with analogue pencils and notebooks and texts, as in the blackout poetry task, will also utilize the boundary object potential of digital pencils. That way, teachers can help learners to combine digital and analogue tools in their own design *in* learning. Of course, teachers can also design learning practices that actualize more strictly digital potentials of the digital pencil – those to the left in Figure 1. Such practices may

have great learning potential, but they may not actualize the digital-analogue boundary object potentials of digital pencils to the same extent.

A first conclusion, then, is that digital pencils may have the potential to function as boundary objects that connect digital classrooms – as most Swedish classrooms – to analogue literacy practices, such as writing and drawing by hand, or performing calculations on a piece of paper.

But, can they also serve the function of introducing digital literacies into still predominantly analogue classrooms in sub-Saharan Africa? This question is more complex, and we can only offer a tentative answer to it, partially, of course, due to the fact that we have not analysed the more analogue classrooms that still dominate in sub-Saharan Africa. However, we want to return to the basic semiotic and pedagogic idea of aptness (Bezemer and Kress, 2016; Kress, 2010). Just like learners in the digitalized classroom need to be able to choose the most apt digital or analogue tool or technique for meaning-making and learning, so should the learners in the predominantly analogue classroom. Even if Tilya's (2018) and others' research on the digitalization of education in Africa says that many African countries still lack strategies (and, in many cases, financial means) for such digitalization processes, they will happen sooner or later. The introduction of digital pencils together with, say, tablets may then offer means of a smoother transition from strictly analogue literacies to more digital school literacies. In other words, learners will not have to leave all their analogue literacy or numeracy skills behind as they move from an analogue to a more digital classroom. In fact, it could be argued that this is partially what happened as part of the rapid digitalization of education in Sweden: everything was supposed to be performed with digital tools on digital devices. In that process pencils and handwriting were to some extent left out of the loop.

So, in many parts of Africa, digital pencils can probably function as boundary objects with a design that connects to those of analogue pencils that can be used to facilitate the transition of analogue literacies into more digital environments – but at the same time not leave the analogue tools to their own destiny in a drawer somewhere.

We also want to return to Tilya's (2018) observation that mobile devices are everywhere in sub-Saharan Africa. We believe in using any literacy tool that is already available, something which is frequently practiced in many parts of Africa (UNESCO, 2020). Therefore we want to end this article with a proposal to the hardware industry. We suggest that the industry develops reasonably priced pencils that can be used together with screens and applications of mobile phones, or those of very basic tablets. If these pencils were distributed in African, analogue classrooms, the benefits of digital pencils as boundary objects connecting to more digital environments would be more directly available to African learners and their teachers.

Above all – looking more broadly to the future digitalization of education in sub-Saharan Africa – we want to stress the importance of letting go of the idea of ‘either or’ when it comes to digital and analogue literacy practices. As this paper has shown, there are tools – such as the digital pencil – which potentially mitigate between the digital and the analogue world. Such tools are best put to use in designs for learning which recognize and make use of all available and apt tools for meaning-making and learning.

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